

Isaiah's conversation with Hezekiah with two pauses
2 Kings 20:17, 19

Part of a longer analysis into the pauses in speech in the Bible

See *A Study in Silence*

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ABSTRACT

After God miraculously extended Hezekiah's life, the king's reception of Babylonian envoys became a divinely permitted test designed to reveal "everything in his heart" (2 Chronicles 32:31). By examining the narrative structure, dialogical omissions, lexical choices and especially the pauses within the exchange between Hezekiah and Isaiah, the study probes the ambiguity of Hezekiah's inner disposition. Rather than resolving the tension, the narrative is ambiguous regarding Hezekiah's motivation. Is Hezekiah humble, resigned, selfish and/or proud? Far from being a weakness in the account, such gaps are seen as deliberate, prompting the reader to enter Isaiah's and Hezekiah's emotional moment personally.

2 Kings 20:17, 19

הָנָה יָמִים בָּאִים וְנִשְׂאָ כָּל־אֲשֶׁר בְּבֵיתְךָ וְאֲשֶׁר אֶצְרֹךְ אֲבֹתֶיךָ עַד־הַיּוֹם הַזֶּה בְּכֶלֶה לֹא־יִנְתָּר דְּבַר אֲמַר יְהוָה
וַיֹּאמֶר חֲזַקְיָהוּ אֶל־יִשְׁעֵיהֶוָה טוֹב דְּבַר־יְהוָה אֲשֶׁר דִּבַּרְתָּ וַיֹּאמֶר הֲלוֹא אִם־שָׁלוֹם וְאַמֶּת יִהְיֶה בְּיָמֵי

When Hezekiah was about to die at the age of 39, he prayed emotively and Jehovah caused Isaiah to tell him that he had seen his tears and he would heal him and give him a further fifteen years. Jehovah went on to assure him saying, "out of the palm of the king of Assyria I shall deliver you and this city, and I will defend this city for my own sake and for the sake of David my servant". Hezekiah asked for a sign that he would recover. In response, Jehovah "made the shadow that had

gone down gradually go back on the steps, that is, on the steps [of the stairs] of Ahaz, ten steps backward” (2 Kings 20:1–11).

News of Hezekiah’s sign, recovery, and defeat of the Assyrians, reached Baladan the king of Babylon. Impressed by this cluster of events and presumably looking for strong allies against the Assyrians, he sent ambassadors to Jerusalem. “And thus it was that by the spokesmen of the princes of Babylon that were sent to him to inquire about the portent that had happened in the land, the [true] God left him to put him to the test, to get to know everything in his heart” (2 Chronicles 32:31). What did God discover? Can we discover anything?

As a result of the defeat of the Assyrians, “Hezekiah came to have riches and glory to a very great amount” (verse 27). So when the princes of Babylon arrived, Hezekiah “rejoiced” (Isaiah 39:2) and he went on to “show them all his treasure-house, the silver and the gold and the balsam oil and the good oil and his armory and all that was to be found in his treasures. There proved to be nothing that Hezekiah did not show them in his own house and in all his dominion” (2 Kings 20:13).

Political alliances were being formed. Hezekiah was keen to show his resources. But did he tell the embassy the real cause of the defeat of Assyria (2 Kings 19:35)? Was that part of the divine test? In the glare of all this fame, had Hezekiah forgotten Jehovah’s* promise that *he* had defended Jerusalem and *he* would continue to do so? We know how Jehovah felt when the nation relied on anyone but on him for their salvation (cf. Isaiah 20:6; 30:2; 31:1). Isaiah was the one who penned those feelings and here was Isaiah coming to see Hezekiah.

2 Kings 20:

14 After that Isaiah the prophet came in to King Hezekiah and said to him: “What did these men say and from where did they proceed to come to you?” So Hezekiah said: “From a distant land they came, from Babylon.” 15 And he went on to say: “What did they see in your house?” To this Hezekiah said: “Everything that is in my house they saw. There proved to be nothing that I did not show them in my treasures.”

On first impressions, Hezekiah’s responses show little guile or dissembling. However, notice that we do not get a response from Isaiah’s question: “What did they

*See Appendix.

say?” So it looks as if Hezekiah was attempting to hide the motive of the Babylonian visitors and the conversations they had.

Isaiah’s next question showed that Isaiah knew what Hezekiah had been doing: “What did they see in your house?” This was much like Jehovah’s questions to Adam and then to Cain (Genesis 3:11; 4:9), which were endeavouring to elicit a full confession. It appears that Hezekiah was happy to answer this question more fully. In fact, he could have stopped after “Everything that is in my house they saw”, but he expanded it to *לֹא־הָיָה דְבַר אֲשֶׁר לֹא־הָרְאִיתֶם בְּאֶצְרֹתַי*, “There proved to be nothing that I did not show them in my treasures”. What is the tone of this response? Was it said in remorse as an acknowledgement of error? Or was it said with enthusiasm, with continued joy for having had such important visitors. Given what Isaiah next said, it would seem that Hezekiah’s tone was still jubilant.

16 Isaiah now said to Hezekiah: “Hear the word of Jehovah, 17 “Look! Days are coming, and all that is in your own house and that your forefathers have stored up down to this day will actually be carried to Babylon. Nothing will be left,” Jehovah has said. 18 “And some of your own sons that will come forth from you to whom you will become father will themselves be taken and actually become court officials in the palace of the king of Babylon.””

Jehovah’s verdict was in two parts with a pause in the midst.

After the prophetic introduction, there are three statements rising in intensity of devastation. Before the pause, Jehovah ruled against Hezekiah’s and the nation’s material possessions. First, the Babylonians would not only take everything in Hezekiah’s house, but they would search on beyond, mirroring verse 13: “There proved to be nothing that Hezekiah did not show them in his own house *and* in all his dominion”. Second, he was to picture empty rooms and empty storehouses: *לֹא־יִתֵּר דְבַר*, “There will not be left a thing”, or even a completely empty land.

After this bleak, stark punishment Jehovah paused.

He no doubt used a hiatus to allow Hezekiah to absorb the weight of those calamitous words.

Isaiah’s prophecy may also have been spoken in stages to underscore the severity of the rising judgment. This is typical Hebrew poetic or prophetic style, where parallel ideas are unfolded with sequentially greater impact.

Perhaps Jehovah paused to allow Hezekiah to repent, to recognise the folly of his

attentions towards the Babylonians. Had Hezekiah showed remorse, the judgement might have come to an end at that point. If that was Jehovah's intent, then he waited without success.

If the first two statements were not distressing enough, Jehovah's judgement prophecy then became more personal. If he had paused for a contrite statement to be made, then the greater personal devastation for Hezekiah would have been intended to strike more pointedly at his heart. Hezekiah is informed that his sons would be carried off to serve the king of Babylon. The alliance that Hezekiah had wanted would come about but with his sons in servitude.

His sons are described first as "your own sons", then "to whom you will become father", which would seem to draw attention to the relationship that Hezekiah had with his children and the horror of knowing that they would be taken away into exile. Sin has effects that often extend beyond the sinner.

19 Hezekiah said to Isaiah: "The word of Jehovah that you have spoken is good." And he went on to say: "Is it not so, if peace and truth themselves will continue in my own days?"

Hezekiah's response came in two parts with a pause.

His first words are somewhat guarded and brief; it was not the open and full admission that we were expecting. What did he mean by "good"? Was he just saying "The word of Jehovah is good" because he was just going through the motions without thinking? Was there any depth to it? Did he mean, in general?—that God's judgements are always good? A sort of, yes fair enough, you are always right? Did he say this because he couldn't bring himself to say that what he had done with the Babylonian ambassadors was bad, so he prevaricated and switched attention to God's goodness. Or should we see in this first sentence a humble submission to the will of his God. After all, it is not always easy to say that correction is good at the time of first hearing it (Hebrews 12:11). Or less positive, a resignation to it. If so, it was still rather thin on penitence.

Then he paused. A number of translations render וַיֹּאמֶר as "For he thought" (NIV, ESV, NASB) or "For the king was thinking" (NLT). This is a possibility. There is no doubt in our minds that the second statement, whether said or thought, is expanding on the first.

Looking more closely at אֵלֹהִים אִם-שָׁלוֹם וְאֱמֶת יְהוָה בְּיָמַי, we see that his first word was אֵלֹהִים,

which should mean that his second comment is a question with the adverb of negation. The brief sentence would literally be, “is not/if/peace/and truth/will be/in my days?”. The parallel in Isaiah 39:8 reads: *כי יהיה שלום ואמת בימי*, “for/will be/peace/and truth/in my days”. In this version, *אם* is replaced with *כי*.

The idea of peace in his days was derived from Jehovah’s promise at the time of his illness (2 Kings 20:6) and the mention that his sons, not himself, would be going into exile.

Why did Hezekiah couple the word *שלום*, “peace” with the word *אמת*, “truth”? *twot* defines *אמת* as “truth, faithfulness, verity”, going on to say that the word “carries [an] underlying sense of certainty, dependability”. Along with mercy and love, it is a characteristic of God’s nature, which leads “to God’s peace toward sinful men”, hence “the word is often coupled with peace”, citing Isaiah 39:8. In other words, Hezekiah knew that this peace and faithfulness were to be evidence of his God’s approval.

Surely he did not mean that the *outcome* of the judgement was good, did he? Maybe. And maybe he did not intend to say anything else but then, on reflection in his pause, decided that his use of the word “good” needed to be explained. *BDB* suggest that *אם* could be translated “it not (good), if ...?” (p. 50), so they believe that Hezekiah is expanding on his unspecific term. In which case, he meant that the judgement was good in that he personally would not be affected. His response seems to focus on his immediate relief rather than the larger implications. So has he actually repented? Montgomery thinks that it might be a self-congratulation.

The *NW 2013* renders the second disclosure as, “It is good if there will be peace and stability during my lifetime”. Are we to take this expression as selfish, ignoring the consequences of his actions, or is he expressing relief at the personal reprieve. Or better, appreciation for Jehovah’s mercy in deferring the judgement? Hezekiah might have hesitated as he tried to reconcile guilt or helplessness about the future judgement and gratitude for God’s mercy.

“And thus it was that by the spokesmen of the princes of Babylon that were sent to him to inquire about the portent that had happened in the land, the [true] God left him to put him to the test, to get to know everything in his heart” (2 Chronicles 32:31). What did *we* discover?

The Bible's "literary convention is for the narrator to report action and dialogue... and not, for the most part, what they think or feel" (Linafelt, *Hebrew*, p. 31). And that is what we have here. Linafelt also wrote that "the importance of this obscurity of motivation can scarcely be overstated for any literary reading [of] biblical narrative, since it...gives the literature its profound complexity [prompting] the reader to negotiate the many possible ways of imagining the characters' inner lives" (*Style*, p. 25).

The pause is an indication of something going on in Hezekiah's inner life. We have asked plenty of questions of the 'obscurity of Hezekiah's motivation'. And here are a few more for which we do not have certain answers. Is the pause evidence of a hesitation? Of a person not passing the test perfectly? Of a person struggling with discipline? He was being upbraided for an ungodly pride so were there vestiges of this pride which caused him to find the reprimand difficult to fully accept?

ABBREVIATIONS AND BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ESV *The Holy Bible, English Standard Version*, Crossway, 2001.
- Linafelt, *Hebrew* Tod Linafelt, *The Hebrew Bible As Literature: A Very Short Introduction*, Oxford University Press, 2016.
- Linafelt, *Style* Tod Linafelt, *On Biblical Style*, The St. John’s Review.
- NASB *The New American Standard Bible*, The Lockman Foundation, 2020.
- NIV *Holy Bible, New International Version*, Hodder and Stoughton, 1980.
- NLT *New Living Translation*, Tyndale House Foundation, 2015.
- NW *New World Translation of the Holy Scriptures, with References*, Watch Tower Bible and Tract Society of Pennsylvania, 1984.
- NW 2013 *New World Translation of the Holy Scriptures (Study Edition)*, Watch Tower Bible and Tract Society of Pennsylvania, 2013.

Bible quotations are from the *New World Translation of the Holy Scriptures, with References*, 1984, unless otherwise indicated.

The Introduction to this edition of NW contains this explanation:

Where “you” is printed in small capital letters, it shows that the pronoun is plural. Also, where the plural number of a verb is not apparent, its plurality is indicated by printing it in small capital letters. If the context already clearly indicates plurality, then no special capitalization is used.

APPENDIX

In the Bible the divine name יהוה occurs almost seven thousand times, more often than any of God's titles, and more often than any other separate Hebrew word.

There are many theophoric names in the Bible. The majority of Bible translators transliterate those names which have the first two syllables of the divine name as Jeho. Hence: Jehonathan, Jehoshua, Jehoshaphat, Jehoahaz, Jehonadab, Jehoram etc. When the Israelites shortened a name they would not abbreviate but they contracted it by removing syllables from the middle of the name. So Jehonathan was reduced to Jonathan; Jehoshua became Joshua; Jehonadab became Jonadab. God's name was contracted to Jah, hence: Elijah, Abijah and Hallelujah etc. Therefore, the divine name must have had three syllables, not two.

We believe that a י is more likely to be transliterated as a y in English, and a ו is more likely to be transliterated as a w. So the divine name could be *Yehowah*. However, most Bible scholars avoid any transliteration. They use the tetragrammaton in Hebrew letters יהוה, or they display the divine name as YHWH. This is all well and good, but it is inconsistent with their transliteration of other Bible names. If they are to be consistent then they should either use Yehonathan for Jonathan or show the Hebrew letters יהנתן, or YWNTN. Sometimes they use *Yahweh* which disregards how names were shortened, and it only has two syllables.

The argument that the vowels of יהוה are those of אֱלֹהֵינוּ does not hold up because the vowels are not the same.

Gesenius pointed out that "Those who consider that יהוה was the actual pronunciation [of God's name] are not altogether without ground on which to defend their opinion. In this way can the abbreviated syllables יהו and יו, with which many proper names begin, be more satisfactorily explained."

We believe that *Jehovah* is a reasonable transliteration of the tetragrammaton.